

**IT TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING,
DISTANCE LEARNING, E-DIGITAL EDUCATION**

Samarqand Shahar Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

academik litseyi. Ingliz tili o`qituvchilari

Egamqulova Iroda Abduqaxorovna

Irgashbekova Nigora Rustamovna.

Annotation: The teaching of foreign languages, especially English, in educational institutions is associated with the creation of an innovative theory of education. This leads to the formation of a relationship in which the child is absorbed in foreign educational achievements in the educational process in order to achieve certain success in reforming the education system, increasing the effectiveness of education, ensuring the socialization of the individual, through the introduction of pedagogical technologies in the education system.

Nowadays, teaching foreign languages, especially English, through the use of innovative methods of teaching plays an important role in the education system. Content development is observed in the entire education system on the basis of pedagogical initiatives and innovations of teachers. It also has a positive impact on the development of the education system as a whole. In short, innovation means a new approach to solving a problem in a particular field of activity. Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society.

Keywords: innovation, education, educational efficiency, pedagogy, English, education system.

Language, which is a means of communication, can be practiced in a natural environment (in the family, in the community) or in an organized lesson. Knowledge of linguistic phenomena is studied theoretically. In today's world of

international relations, knowledge of languages and multilingualism is of great importance

In general, pedagogy is developing rapidly. Concepts such as innovation in education, innovative activity, innovative pedagogy, management of innovative processes in education, learning foreign languages, teaching in a foreign language have emerged. In our country, the organization of teaching foreign languages and teaching in all educational institutions, starting from preschool, is rising to a new level. This is evidenced by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On further improving the system of learning foreign languages" dated December 10, 2012 and the introduction of continuous teaching of foreign languages in the first grades of secondary schools from the 2013-2014 academic year. Today, the reason for learning a foreign language, especially English, is to focus on this innovative process as a key factor in achieving the achievements of world science and development in order to join the ranks of developed countries in science, culture and economy.

Education develops a country's economy and society; therefore, it is the milestone of a nation's development. Education provides knowledge and skills to the population, as well as shaping the personality of the youth of a nation. Nevertheless, can education shape the youth's national identity? Can education cultivate the person's identity or sense of belonging to the nation? Education is very important for an individual's success in life. It can give a big impact on human opportunity in continuing their life quality. Education is generally seen as the foundation of society which brings economic wealth, social prosperity and political stability. Economic and social status depends on education obtained by individual since education contributes to individual capability in managing quality of life. Technological innovations are having a significant impact on educational systems at all levels. Online courses, teaching aids, educational software, social networking tools, and other emerging technologies are disrupting the traditional

classroom environment. Understanding the effects that technological innovations have on students, teachers, and schools is critical to developing strategies and techniques to manage and use technology in education.

There are the top six technology innovations that are causing major changes in education: Virtual reality (VR) technology Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Cloud Computing for Education 3D Printing Academic Research in Educational Sciences VOLUME 2 | CSPI CONFERENCE 2 | 2021 Innovative Technologies in Teaching Foreign Languages and Learner Assessment in Online Education Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region Google Scholar Scientific Library of Uzbekistan Academic Research, Uzbekistan 534 www.ares.uz Social Media in Educational Institutions The Use of Biometrics in Schools In the current context, innovative technologies are directly related to the development of higher education, both in terms of content and organizational structure. The basis of these processes has been the rapid development of the theory of pedagogical education over the last three decades.(A.A.Abdulina, Ye.V.Bondarevskaya, V.I.Zagvyazinskiy, V.S.Ilin, N.M.Kan-Kalik, V.A.Slastenin).

Innovative educational technologies are based on three main components:

- Modern, well-structured structure, the basis of which is the competence in professional activity that meets the current realities of entrepreneurial activity. content includes a variety of multimedia materials transmitted through modern means of communication.
- Use of modern, innovative teaching methods. Such methods should be aimed at developing the competencies of the future specialist, involving students in active knowledge and practical activities, showing initiative in the learning process. Passive assimilation of educational programs is excluded.

1. Availability of modern infrastructure in the educational process. It should be based on the information, technological, organizational and communication

components that help to apply new forms and methods of teaching, in particular distance learning. Innovative technologies in education are based on the application of certain approaches to teaching, ie. principles that take into account the requirements and objectives that underlie the development of new technologies.

All innovations in the field of pedagogy are based on strict adherence to the current stage of socio-economic development of society. At present, they should focus on developing students' independence, developing self-study and self-improvement skills, and mastering curricula consciously rather than mechanically.

Innovative technologies in education are constantly evolving and expanding. The following main technology groups can be distinguished:

1. Information and communication technologies or ICT in the field of research. The use of these technologies is associated with the development of the information society and the active introduction of the media in all spheres of life. Such technologies are aimed at informing the minds of students. Curricula include new disciplines in computer science, information processes, and ICT. The educational process is also being actively informed to help teachers and students improve their information culture;

2. Person-centered technologies. These technologies are designed to prioritize the education and upbringing of the individual. The whole educational process is focused on the development of the individual, taking into account the individuality and developmental characteristics of the individual.

Innovative technologies in education allow us to organize education and direct it in the right direction. People have always been afraid of the unknown and new things, they have reacted negatively to any change. Stereotypes that exist in the public mind and affect normal lifestyles lead to painful events, preventing the renewal of all forms of education. The reason people don't want to embrace innovations in modern education is because they are blocking vital needs for

convenience, security, and self-affirmation. Not everyone is ready to re-learn theory, take an exam, change their mind, and spend personal time and money. Once the update process has started, you can only stop it using special methods.

Innovation in education involves a system of several components:

- learning objectives;
- educational content;
- motivation and teaching aids;
- process participants (students, teachers);
- Performance results.

In conclusion, it should be noted that information and communication technologies have become commonplace in kindergartens, schools, academies and universities.

REFERENCES

1. Ananiadou, K. & Claro, M. (2009). 21st century skills and competences for new millennium learners in OECD countries. OECD education working papers (vol. 41, pp. 1–33). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/218525261154>.
2. Bennett, S., Maton, K., & Kervin, L. (2008). The ‘digital natives’ debate: A critical review of the evidence. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 39(5), 775-786. doi:10.1111/j.1467-8535.2007.00793.x
3. Bonpatron.com (n.d.) Accessed August 16, 2020 at: <https://bonpatron.com/fr/>
4. Bekmuratova U.B. Essay on "The use of innovative technologies in teaching English." Tashkent - 2012 Otaboeva, M. R. Use of modern innovative technologies in foreign language teaching and its effectiveness;
5. Cadre de références de la compétence numérique, réalisé par le ministère de l'Éducation et de l'Enseignement supérieur du Québec (Canada). (2019). Ministère de l'Éducation et de l'Enseignement supérieur.

6. Minamatov, Y. E. U. (2021). APPLICATION OF MODULAR TEASHING TESHNOLOGY IN TESHNOLOGY. Sscientifis progress, 2 (8), 911-913.
7. Okhunov, M., & Minamatov, Y. (2021). Application of Innovative Projects in Information Systems. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 11, 167-168.
8. Karimov, O., Karimova, G., & Karimov, O. (2021). INFORMATION IN THE FIELD OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION. Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research, 1 (1), 103-110.